

Traditional Healthcare Practices of the Bodo Tribes: An Investigation of Plant-Based Medicinal Knowledge in Sonitpur District of Assam, India

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Abstract: This research investigates the ethno-medicinal practices and plant-based knowledge of the Bodo community in Sonitpur, Assam, India. A total of 55 respondents from 8 villages participated in the survey, revealing the use of 53 plant species belonging to 36 families for treating various ailments. The Relative Frequency of Citation (RFC) and Use Value (UV) were calculated to determine the significance of each plant species. *Colocasia* species emerged as a key medicinal plant, with RFC and UV values of 0.70 and 0.89 respectively, underscoring its importance in local healthcare traditions. The study highlights the diverse ethnomedicinal uses of plants among the Bodo tribes and provides valuable insights into their traditional healthcare practices.

Keywords: Bodo community, Conservation, Ethnomedicinal plants, Indigenous knowledge, Healthcare practices

I. INTRODUCTION

Our planet is rich in biodiversity, with medicinal plants playing a vital role in addressing human health issues. Approximately 80% of the global population depends on traditional herbal remedies to meet their healthcare needs [17], [10]. Many developing nations around the world depend on plant-based remedies to address various health issues [19]. India is home to a considerable share of the world's forests, covering around two-thirds of the global forest area. Traditional knowledge and herbal remedies continue to hold significant value for Indians, playing a vital role in their primary healthcare and daily lives [4]. India's forest-dwelling tribal communities have a strong bond with the natural world and utilize traditional medicine, including medicinal plants, to manage health problems and diseases [6]. Traditional medicines have been used from several thousand years and traditional knowledge of medicinal plants also known as herbal medicines and it is considered as the oldest forms of the health care system known to mankind on this world [13].

In India, especially the northeastern region, ethnic communities have a rich history of using natural plant remedies to treat various health problems [7]. Ethnic community in Northeast India incorporate plant-based natural remedies into their daily lives for various purposes, including medicine, nutrition, and decoration, while researchers are actively documenting the therapeutic properties of diverse plant species in the region [7]. The Bodo community, one of the largest indigenous groups in Assam, possesses rich ethnobotanical knowledge rooted in generations of experience and close interaction with nature. Assam's tropical climate, with its ample rainfall and high moisture levels, supports an ideal environment for dense vegetation with great variety of plants like trees, herbs, shrubs and climbers, etc. making a blend of semi-evergreen forests and scattered grasslands [20]. Assam is rich with more than 200 medicinal plants that have got value because of their uses in the country itself [16].

Sonitpur district positioned in the state of Assam, is populated by the bodo community and they believe on indigenous knowledge of wild flora and fauna resources for medicine, food and different purposes [15]. They depend on various flora and fauna as medicine in their primary health care to get cure and safety from the minor diseases [15]. With centuries of experience and association with the nature, the Bodo people possess a deep insight into the therapeutic uses of plants. The ethnic tribal villagers depend on herbal medicine or natural remedy for any kind of ailments such as minor bodily disorders (fever, intestinal worm, cold and cough, headache, jaundice, etc.) [22].

Recording and conserving traditional knowledge systems, which embody a community's distinct cultural heritage, is vital for effective bioresource management and in fighting mysterious illnesses [24]. Consequently, traditional knowledge has become a focal point for research and development of new products with added value [15]. However, few reports of usage of ethnomedicinal plants from Sonitpur district have been found documented. Therefore, the current study aims to document and provide the traditional knowledge for the sustainable utilization of medicinal plants among the bodo community of Sonitpur district of Assam.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Study Area

The current study was carried out in the Sonitpur district which is located in the northern region of Assam and lies between 26°30' N to 27°01' N latitude and 92°16' E to 93°43' E longitude covering a total area of about 2076.70 km². The district is girded by Arunachal Pradesh in the North, Jorhat districts in the South, Biswanath district in the East and Morigaon, Nagaon, and Darrang district in the West. Sonitpur district experiences a humid subtropical climate with an average annual rainfall of approximately 160.300 mm and maintaining a relative humidity of around 87%. The region experiences a mild climate, characterized by pleasant temperatures during the winter season. The study was performed in 8 villages (Tezpur, Balipara, Dhekiajuli, Chariduar, Naduar, Bhalukpung, Rangapara, Jamuguri) of Sonitpur district as shown in Fig 1.

B. Selection of Respondents

The key respondents were selected those who had an extreme knowledge about the different uses of plants and at least 10 years of practical experienced in demonstrating the acquired skills. The interview was carried out with forest dwellers, farmers, elderly and old aged people ranged from 30-70 years, who possess the ethnomedicinal knowledge of plants. Interviews were carried out in the informant's native language, lasting between 40 to 60 minutes. To ensure privacy, interviews were conducted anonymously, and all collected information was treated as confidential.

C. Data collection

A field survey was carried out for the collection of data from January 2024 to March 2025. The data was collected through household questionnaires and semi-structured interviews with the respondents of villages of Sonitpur district, Assam. The interviews usually covered the basic information, local name, parts used, methods of preparation, medicinal value. The therapeutical uses of plants were recorded via interacting with rural women and practitioners. Nomenclature of plant specimens were updated according to online resources, including POWO (Plant of World Online) and IPNI (The International Plant Name Index) [5]. Photographs of plant specimen along with flowers, fruits, etc. were captured with digital and phone camera.

D. Data analysis

1. *Relative Frequency Citation (RFC)*: The RFC index evaluates the local importance and usage of plant species based on citation frequency, using a defined formula for calculation [23].

$$RFC = FC/N, (0 \leq RFC \leq 1)$$

where FC represents the number of respondents using a particular species and N is the total number of survey participants.

2. *Use value (UV)*: The Use Value (UV) index was used to evaluate the relative importance of plant species providing insight into the most favored species among respondents for medicinal purposes [21], [26].

$$UV = \sum U/n$$

Here, U represents the total number of uses of fish species reported by respondents, and n is the total

number of respondents surveyed.

III. RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS

A. Socio-demographic Profile

A total of 55 respondents were participated by the Bodo people of 8 villages of Sonitpur district, comprising 35 males and 20 females. Some respondents were affable, cooperative, hospitable and willingly agreed to participate in the survey whereas some respondents were refused to participate in the survey. The interview was carried out with elderly and old aged people ranged from 30-70 years, who possess the knowledge of ethnomedicinal value of plants. Participants represented various occupations, including ojhas (practitioners), farmers, housewives as shown in table 1.

B. Relative Frequency of Citation (RFC) and Use Value (UV)

The Relative Frequency of Citation (RFC) value of all the plant species lies between 0.03 and 0.76 whereas, the Use Value (UV) lies between 0.08 and 0.89 (Table 2). *Allium sativum* (0.76) has the highest RCF value, whereas *Aloe barbadensis miller* (0.03) has the lowest RCF value. The highest UV was observed for *Colocasia species* (0.89), whereas, the lowest UV was observed for *Aloe barbadensis miller* (0.08) as shown in table 2.

C. Ethno-medicinal uses of plants

The present study records the ethnomedicinal uses of species among the Bodo tribes in Sonitpur district of Assam. A total number of 53 plants species are identified belonging to 36 families, which were used by Bodo tribes of Sonitpur district for treatment of various ailments. These 53 plant species belongs to the family Lamiaceae families containing four species; Fabaceae, Myrtaceae, Rubiaceae containing three species; Apiaceae, Araceae, Lythraceae, Combretaceae, Cucurbitaceae, Malvaceae, Rutaceae, and Zingiberaceae families containing two species each; Acanthaceae, Amaryllidaceae, Anacardiaceae, Anteraceae, Apocynaceae, Asphodelaceae, Asteraceae, Caracaceae, Caryophyllaceae, Compositae, Crassulaceae, Dilleniaceae, Hypericaceae, Lauraceae, Linderniaceae, Meliaceae, Moringaceae, Musaceae, Phyllanthaceae, Piparaceae, Poaceae, Rutaceae, Saururaceae, Scrophulariaceae, families containing one species each. The scientific name, local name (Bodo), parts used, and mode of usage are summarized where species are arranged alphabetically by genus as shown in table 2.

IV. DISCUSSION

Our research reveals that the Bodo community in Sonitpur district utilizes various plant species for medicinal purposes. Similarly, 53 plant species are reportedly used by the ethnic communities in Sonitpur district for their health benefits. The collected plant species were herbs (38%), trees (30%), shrubs (26%), climbers (6%) as shown in Fig 2(A). The parts such as leaves (32), fruits (17), stems (6) and flower (6), rhizome (2), bulb (1) as shown in Fig 1(B) were reported to be used for treatment of various ailments such as dysentery, Tooth pain, Eye redness, eye irritation, high blood pressure, constipation, gastric, cough, cold fever, chickenpox, etc.

This study found that leaves are a common part used in traditional medicine preparation. The evaluation of UV and RFC values revealed that *Colocasia species* are highly utilized by the Bodo community for health benefits. The high RFC and UV values of *Allium sativum* and *Colocasia esculata* respectively indicate their popularity and frequent use in traditional medicine. Bodo women play a significant role in preparing traditional medicine, using simple methods that vary depending on the ailment. The plants are often consumed cooked, boiled or raw, or applied externally to aid in recovery, similar studies have been reported by the Baro *et al.*,[5].

The current study also recognized unique uses of different parts of plant species. For example, flowers of *Spondias pinnata* are boiled or cooked with small indigenous fishes is reported to treat dysentery and traditionally believed to be fast healing. Consumption of *Syzygium aromaticum* is traditionally believed to relieve the pain of teeth caused by tooth decay. Moreover, *Solena amplexicaulis* is traditionally believed to treat rashes of chickenpox and *Spilanthes paniculata* is used to treat mouth ulcer. The use of plants like *Ocimum tenuiflorum* and *Piper nigrum* for respiratory issues, and *Terminalia bellirica* and *Terminalia chebula* for gastrointestinal problems, aligns with existing

literature on ethnomedicinal practices. The study also highlights the use of lesser-known plants, such as *Clerodendrum infortunatum* for ringworm [5] and *Spilanthes paniculata* for immunity booster, *Lindernia pusilla* for Jaundice.

However, by prioritizing the cultivation and protection of these valuable plant species, we can help safeguard the health and well-being of indigenous communities while also preserving our precious natural heritage [4]. Various plant species are identified for their ethno-medicinal value but they are near existence due to human activities such as over grazing, industrialization, over harvesting, etc. The study's findings have significant implications for healthcare and conservation. The reliance on traditional medicine underscores the need for further research into the efficacy and safety of these plant-based remedies.

V. CONCLUSION

This study contributes to the growing body of evidence on the importance of traditional medicine in primary healthcare. The documentation of ethnomedicinal practices and plant species used by the Bodo tribes of Sonitpur district of Assam can inform healthcare policies and conservation efforts, ultimately promoting the sustainable use of natural resources and the preservation of traditional knowledge. The study's findings can also inform the development of new drugs and therapies, and promote the integration of traditional medicine into mainstream healthcare. Our findings indicate that the local community still relies heavily on medicinal plants for primary healthcare, preserving traditional practices despite modernization. Given the importance of these plants in primary healthcare, it's crucial to promote their cultivation and conservation. However, the younger generation's waning interest in traditional medicine and urban migration pose a threat to this knowledge. To address this, efforts should be made to motivate young people to preserve and pass on this valuable traditional knowledge for the benefit of future generations.

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Fig 1. Picture representing the map of sonitpur, Assam and India.

TABLE 1: DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS PARTICIPATING IN STUDY.

Variable	Category	Number
Gender	Male	35
	Female	20
Age groups	30-40	15
	40-50	10
	50-60	18
	60-70	12
Occupation	Farmer	29
	Housewife	14
	Practitioner	12

Fig 2: (A) Different life forms used in traditional medicines plants by the Bodo community of Sonitpur district. (B) Plants parts used in curing different diseases by the Bodo people of Sonitpur district, Assam.

TABLE 2: ETHNOMEDICINAL USES OF PLANT SPECIES OF SONITPUR, ASSAM, INDIA

Sl. No	Scientific name	Local name	Family (Life form)	Parts used	Mode of usage	Disease condition	RCF	UV
1	<i>Allium sativum</i> L.	sambrang gufur	Amaryllidaceae (Herb)	Bulb	Paste is cooked with oil and is smelled through nose.	Runny nose	0.76	0.81
2	<i>Aloe barbadensis miller</i> (L.) Burn. f	aloevera	Asphodelaceae (shrub)	Leaves	Extracted juice is mixed with water, which is then applied directly to the skin.	Liver, Glowing skin	0.03	0.08
3	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i> (Burm.f.) Nees	sirota	Acanthaceae (shrub)	Leaves, stems	Extracted juice is consumed.	Helminthiasis	0.18	0.27
4	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A. Juss	neem	Meliaceae (tree)	Leaves, stems	Leaves are directly taken/ boiled with water and it is used in bath time. Stem is used as a toothbrush.	Skin diseases, lice, tooth plague.	0.36	0.70
5	<i>Bacopa monnieri</i> (L.) Wettst.	bramhi mwigong	Scrophulariaceae (herb)	Leaves	Leaves are consumed at a meal.	Weak memory	0.16	0.27
6	<i>Bryophyllum pinnatum</i> (Lam.) Pers.	pategaja	Crassulaceae (herb)	Leaves,	Extracted juice is consumed daily.	Kidney stone, urinary issues.	0.38	0.65
7	<i>Cajanus cajan</i> (L.) Mill	khokhleng	Fabaceae (shrub)	Leaves	Extracted juice is taken twice daily for 5 to 7 days.	Jaundice, pneumonia, liver	0.34	0.45
8	<i>Carica papaya</i> L.; MB033	mwmwmp hul	Caracaceae (tree)	Fruits, flowers	Boiled or cooked fruits or flowers is consumed.	Stomach problem, constipation	0.40	0.69
9	<i>Centella asiatica</i> (L.) Urb.	Manimunig idir	Apiaceae (herb)	Leaves	Extracted juice is taken twice daily.	Acidity and stomach issues	0.43	0.63
10	<i>Cinnamomum tamala</i> (Buch. Ham)	tezpaat bilai	Lauraceae (tree)	Leaves	Dried leaves are boiled with water and is consumed	Throat issues	0.12	0.27
11	<i>Citrus limon</i> L. Osbeck	kharji	Rutaceae (tree)	Fruits	Extracted Juice is consumed.	Indigestion, skin issues	0.21	0.41
12	<i>Cocos nucifera</i> L.	narengkhol	Araceae (tree)	Fruits	Young fruits are ground and extracted juice is taken in empty stomach.	Kidney stone	0.05	0.09
13	<i>Colocasia esculanta</i> (L.) Schott	gswm thaso	Araceae(herb)	Leaves	Cooked leaves are taken as meal items.	Low iron.	0.70	0.89
				Stem	Stem sap is applied on the affected area.	boils.	0.36	0.24
14	<i>Corchorus capsularis</i> L.	fathw	Malvaceae (herb)	Leaves	Cooked/boiled is consumed.	Diabetes	0.27	0.27
15	<i>Clerodendrum infortunatum</i> L	mwxhna bilai	Lamiaceae (shrub)	Leaves	Pasted is applied on infected area.	Ringworm	0.16	0.09
16	<i>Curcuma longa</i> L.	Haaldwi	Zingiberaceae (herb)	Rhizome	Extracted juice is mixed with water/milk and is consumed.	Relieve pain	0.63	0.54
17	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) pers.	dubri hagra	Poaceae (herb)	Leaves and stems	Leaves along with stems are mixed with water and used in eye.	Eye issues	0.32	0.14
18	<i>Dillenia indica</i> L.	thaigir	Dilleniaceae (tree)	Fruits	Mucous of fruits is applied on hair.	Hair fall, dry hair	0.25	0.25
19	<i>Drymaria cordata</i> (L.) WILLD. ex. Schult	sanmwjink hri	Caryophyllaceae (herb)	Leaves	Extracted juice is taken.	Pneumonia, Jaundice	0.21	0.34
20	<i>Enhydra fluctuans</i> Lour	helangshi	Compositae (herb)	Leaves and Stem	Cooked or boiled leaves and stems is taken as a meal.	Weak eyesight.	0.36	0.45
21	<i>Hibiscus rosa sinensis</i> L.	joba bibar	Malvaceae (shrub)	Flower and leaves	Paste of flower and leaves is directly applied on hairs.	Hair growth, rough hair	0.18	0.36
22	<i>Houttuynia cordata</i> Thumb.	maisundri	Saururaceae (herb)	Leaves	Cooked and boiled Leaves is consumed.	Dysentery	0.27	0.36
23	<i>Hydrocotyle sibthorpioides</i> Lam.	manimuni fisa	Apiaceae (herb)	Leaves	Extracted juice is taken. Cooked or boiled whole plants is also consumed	Stomach issues and jaundice.	0.36	0.65
24	<i>Hypericum japonicum</i> Thumb. Ex Murr	sonapuli	Hypericaceae (herb)	Leaves, stem	Leaves are ground and extracted juice is consumed.	Jaundice, pneumonia	0.18	0.23
25	<i>Lawsonia inermis</i> L.; MB135	jenthokha	Lythraceae (shrub)	Leaves	Paste is applied on hair and nails.	High pressure, damage hair, onchomycosis	0.54	0.72
26	<i>Leucas plukenetii</i> (Roth) Spreng	dhorongphol	Lamiaceae (shrub)	Leaves	Extracted juice is instilled into the nasal passage or cooked leaves are also taken.	Nose bleeding, sinus	0.20	0.74
27	<i>Lindernia pusilla</i> (Willd.) Bold	vuitita	Linderniaceae (Herb)	Leaves	Extracted juice is consumed.	Jaundice	0.27	0.56
28	<i>Momordica charantia</i> L.	khakrel	Cucurbitaceae (climber)	Fruits	Extracted juice is consumed.	Diabetes	0.36	0.69
29	<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lann.	sojona	Moringaceae (tree)	Leaves, fruits	Cooked leaves and fruits are taken as a meal.	Immunity, diabetes	0.34	0.45

30	<i>Murraya koenigii</i> (L.) Spreng.	nwrsing	Rutaceae (shrub)	Leaves	Boiled or cooked is taken as a meal.	Indigestion, weakness	0.27	0.49
31	<i>Musa balbisiana</i> Colla	thair aitha	Musaceae (herb)	Fruits	Riped fruit is consumed.	Diarrhea	0.12	0.36
				Flower	Cooked or boiled is consumed.	Darkspots on skin.		
32	<i>Ocimum tenuiflorum</i> Linn.	thlungsi	Lamiaceae (shrub)	Leaves	Extracted leaf juice is blended with ginger juice and honey, and taken orally.	Cough and fever.	0.38	0.67
33	<i>Oldenlandia corymbosa</i> L.	ferengi banlu	Rubiaceae (shrub)	Fruits	Fruits are used in herbal capsule plants.	Pneumonia, jaundice	0.16	0.56
34	<i>Paederia foetida</i> Linn.	khifibendwng	Rubiaceae (climber)	Leaves	Cooked or boiled leaves is consumed	Stomach issues	0.36	0.52
35	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> L.	amlafithai	Phyllanthaceae (tree)	Fruits	Raw is consumed.	Immunity, constipation, dull hair	0.27	0.63
36	<i>Piper nigrum</i> L.	jaluk	Piperaceae (tree)	Fruits	Boiled with water/red tea or added with curry.	Cold fever, cough, pneumonia	0.36	0.70
37	<i>Plectranthus ternifolius</i> D. Don	jwglauri	Lamiaceae (shrub)	Leaves	Boiled or cooked leaves is consumed.	Malaria, constipation	0.20	0.29
38	<i>Psidium guajava</i> L.	somfrenng	Myrtaceae (tree)	Leaves	4-5 young leaves are chewed.	Stomach pain.	0.40	0.72
39	<i>Punica granatum</i> L.	dalim fithai	Lythraceae (tree)	Fruits	Raw fruits are consumed.	Anemia	0.52	0.74
40	<i>Scleromitron diffusum</i> (Willd.) R.J. Wang	korpojiba	Rubiaceae (herb)	Leaves	Extracted juice is consumed.	Jaundice	0.20	0.36
41	<i>Senna occidentalis</i> (L.) Link	solleng	Fabaceae (shrub)	Leaves	Cooked or boiled leaves is consumed	Jaundice	0.50	0.76
42	<i>Solena amplexicaulis</i> (Lam.) Gandhi	lwnthi laifang	Cucurbitaceae (climber)	Leaves	Paste is used in rashes areas.	Chickenpox rashes	0.07	0.09
43	<i>Spilanthes paniculata</i> Wall. ex. DC	jari laifang	Anteraceae (herb)	Leaves, flowers	Cooked or boiled Leaves is consumed, and raw flower is consumed.	Immune system, mouth ulcer.	0.47	0.85
44	<i>Spondias pinnata</i> (L.f.) Kurz	thaisuri	Anacardiaceae (herb)	Flowers	Flowers are boiled or cooked with small indigenous fishes.	Dysentery	0.07	0.16
45	<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i> (L.) Merr. et L.M.Perry	loung	Myrtaceae (tree)	Fruits	1-2 pieces are chewed.	Tooth pain	0.07	0.09
46	<i>Syzygium cumini</i> (L.) Skeels.	jam	Myrtaceae (tree)	Fruits	Extracted juice is consumed.	Stomach pain, indigestion.	0.24	0.32
47	<i>Tabernaemontana divaricata</i> (L.) R.Br. ex Roem. and Schult	katantha	Apocynaceae (shrub)	Flower	1-2 drops of extracted Juice of flower are applied on eye.	Eye redness, eye irritation.	0.14	0.29
48	<i>Tamarindus indica</i> L.	thengkhleng	Fabaceae (tree)	Fruits	Ripen fruits are soaked in water and liquid is consumed.	High blood pressure	0.25	0.60
49	<i>Terminalia bellirica</i> (Gaertn.) Roxb.	bhomra	Combretaceae (tree)	Fruits	Powder prepared by dry fruits is mixed with water and is consumed.	Constipation, gastric	0.16	0.32
50	<i>Terminalia Chebula</i> Retz.	silikha	Combretaceae (tree)	Fruits	Raw is consumed or Powder prepared by dry fruits is mixed in water and is consumed.	Constipation, gastric	0.29	0.47
51	<i>Wedelia trilobata</i> (L.) Hitchc	bhringraj	Asteraceae (herb)	Leaves	Extracted juice is applied on hair, scalp.	Scalp itching, dandruff	0.36	0.64
52	<i>Zanthoxylum alatum</i> Roxb	jabrang	Rutaceae (shrub)	Fruits	Fruits are added in curry,or chutney.	Cough, cold fever	0.52	0.74
53	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> Roscoe	haijeng	Zingiberaceae (herb)	Rhizome	Extracted juice is used.	Cough, Fever	0.60	0.74

APPENDICES

A. *Prova Ramchiary*

B. *Andrographis paniculata*

C. *Azadirachta indica*

D. *Bryophyllum pinnatum*

E. *Cajanus cajan*

F. *Carica papaya*

G. *Colocasia esculanta*

H. *Corchorus capsularis*

I. *Drymaria cordata*

J. *Enhydra fluctuans*

K. *Hibiscus rosa*

L. *Hypericum japonicum*

M. Lawsonia inermis

N. Murraya koenigii

O. Musa balbisiana

P. Ocimum tenuiflorum

Q. Oldenlandia corymbosa

R. Psidium guajava

S. Scleromitrion diffusum

T. Senna occidentalis

U. Spilanthes paniculata

V. *Tabernaemontana divaricate*

W. *Terminalia Chebula*

X. *Wedelia trilobata*

Fig 3: Photographs of medicinal plants used by the Bodo people of Sonitpur district, Assam